

Squamous Cell Lung Carcinoma with *ROS1CD74-ROS1* Fusion 76% Rearrangement and *PDL-1* 50% TPS: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

In the Philippines, lung cancer is the 4th most frequent cancer among women. Adenocarcinoma is the predominant histology type among females, worldwide. Squamous cell lung carcinoma is most associated with familial clustering of cancer, particularly among women. *ROS1* rearrangements are extremely rare in squamous cell lung carcinoma (less than 0.2% of cases). Squamous cell lung cancer typically has higher *PD-L1* expression than adenocarcinoma. Most *ROS1*-positive tumors do not express *PD-L1* and have a low tumor mutational burden. The correlation between *ROS1* rearrangements and *PD-L1* overexpression is the least investigated among the druggable translocations in NSCLC.

Here is presented a 69-year-old female, nonsmoker with poorly differentiated squamous cell lung carcinoma presenting a massive right upper lung mass adherent to the middle mediastinal structures, with pleural effusion, with *ROS1CD74-ROS1* fusion 76% rearrangement and *PDL-1* 50% TPS, with several co-morbidities and a strong family history of cancer.

Keywords: Squamous Cell Lung Cancer; *ROS-1*; *PDL-1*; Case report

INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer is the lead cause of cancer death in the world. Its main histologic subtypes are adenocarcinoma (AC), squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), and small cell lung carcinoma (SCLC), which are of distinct etiology, biomarkers, and treatment. The incidence rate of SCC, AC, and SCLC varied across regions, of which the highest rate of SCC, AC, and SCLC was in Eastern Europe, Eastern Asia, and Western Europe. AC was the dominant histologic subtype in females and SCC in males.^[1]

In the Philippines, cancer is second top cause of death, led by lung cancer.^[2,3] Templo FS^[4] indicated that among Filipinos (year 1998–2006; n=107), AC was the most common subtype (57%), followed by SCC (39.6%) and large cell neuroendocrine

carcinoma (LCNEC; 3.7%). SCC and AC occurred in males at 48.6% and 45.9%, respectively, while AC was most common in females at 81.2%. The mean age of males was 61.6 years and 52.6 years in females. In the period 2006–2013 (n=219), the mean age of males was 74.6 years and 53.7 years for females. AC was the most common (85%), followed by SCC (13%) and LCNEC (2%). AC was the most common subtype in males at 83% and SCC dropped to 14%, while AC was still the most common in females at 89.4%.

Tobacco use causes the vast majority of lung cancers in both sexes. Many studies have suggested that women have an increased susceptibility to the carcinogenic effect of tobacco smoke, however one in five women who develop lung cancer are lifelong nonsmokers. The incidence of lung cancer in never-smoking women is higher than that seen in never-smoking men. Environmental exposures, genetic constitution, hormonal factors, and viral infection may each have a role to play in lung cancer development in women.^[5]

More patients with squamous and large cell lung carcinomas reported two or more relatives with cancer, and overall, women reported more family history of cancer. Squamous cell lung carcinoma is most associated with familial clustering of cancer, particularly among women, persons younger than 57 years, and individuals who smoked for fewer than 20 years.^[6]

The presence of a malignant pleural effusion automatically classifies patients to advanced cancer stage and it is associated with significant mortality and morbidity.^[7]

CASE REPORT

This case is of a Filipino 69 year old female, nonsmoker, with persistent cough, s/p biopsy right upper lung mass (31 January 2024) indicating poorly differentiated squamous cell lung carcinoma with pleural effusion (T4N3M1a), EGFR/ALK/BRAF/ERBB2/KRAS/MET/RET alteration negative, 5 Muts/Mb (low TMB), MS-stable, but with ROS1CD74-ROS1 fusion 76% rearrangement and PDL-1 50% TPS.

She gave her written informed consent for this report including the PETCT scan, CT scan, VATS and bronchoscopy images in favor for continuing medical education of the scientific community. Ethical review committee approval was given.

The patient's mother was diagnosed with hepatocellular carcinoma. Her first maternal aunt was diagnosed with lung adenocarcinoma. Her second maternal aunt was diagnosed with two primary cancers: breast cancer and bronchoalveolar carcinoma. Her maternal uncle was diagnosed with pancreatic cancer. Three of the patient's maternal cousins have also been diagnosed with cancer: two cousins with breast cancer both in remission and one cousin with prostate cancer.

The patient is also being treated for bronchial asthma, hypertension stage 2, type 2 diabetes, dyslipidemia, and sinus nodal dysfunction.

PETCT Scan (7 February 2024; Figure 1) showed a 4.5 x 4.8 x 4.4 cm mass at the anterior segment, right upper lung with enlarged lymph nodes in the paratracheal, perivascular, pre-carinal, right hilar region, largest at 1.5 cm. There were liver cysts. Crisotinib was started March 2024.

PETCT Scan (21 June 2024; Figure 2) showed increased RUL mass size to 6.5 x 7.6 x 7.2 cm abutting and compressing adjacent subcostal and mediastinal pleurae; the lymph nodes (bilateral jugulo-carotid, right hilar, mediastinal) regressed but with enlarged FDG-avid right supraclavicular lymph node; with minimal pleural effusion.

EBRT 30 Gy was given to the pending SVC due the mediastinal mass from 9-23 July 2024. Lorlatinib was started July 2024. Carboplatin-Pemetrexed was started 23 August 2024 (1 cycle) then shifted to Carboplatin-Paclitaxel-Pembrolizumab in September to November 2024 (3 cycles), interrupted by bouts of obstructive pneumonia.

CT scan of neck with contrast (24 August 2024) showed ill-defined mass 2.9 x 2.7 cm in right supraclavicular region, clinically protruding, hard, with few sub-centimeter cervical lymph nodes. EBRT 30 GY was given to this enlarged LN from 27 August 2024 to 12 September 2024, with favorable target mass regression.

Chest CT scan (hi-resolution with contrast; 15 November 2024; Figure 3) showed pleural effusion with associated passive atelectasis. Loculated components were seen in the superior and inferior right hemithorax measuring up to 6.5 x 7.4 x 6.8 cm (170cc); pneumonia with consolidation in right to lower lung and mediastinal lymphadenopathy considered.

Video-assisted thoracic surgery (VATS) was done on 23 November 2024 with de-loculation freeing the entrapped right middle and lower lobes, and talc pleurodesis for persistent parapneumonic loculated pleural effusion. Video revealed the whole right upper lobe a hard dense violaceous mass adherent to the middle mediastinal structures, without visible lymph nodes (see Figure 4). Via bronchoscopy (Figure 5), mass was obstructing whole right upper lung lobe (9 January 2025).

Fig 4: RUL mass adherent to middle mediastinal structures, VATS

Fig 5: Mass obstructing RUL, bronchoscopy

Fig 6: CXR, worsening lung infection

In the course of her illness, she had frequent obstructive pneumonia (see 23 January 2025 CXR Figure 6) treated with antibacterial/ antifungal drugs, fever, troublesome cough with hemoptysis. She also had low WBC sometimes needing filgrastim, low hemoglobin needing erythropoietin and sometimes blood transfusion, and lorlatinib-related psoriasis-form rash Grade 2 (symptomatically managed; resolved when lorlatinib was deferred and recurred when resumed the drug).

DISCUSSION

Approximately 1–2% of NSCLC patients harbor tumors that are driven by ROS1 fusion proteins and several different 5' fusion partners for ROS1.^[8,9] ROS1 rearrangements are more common in lung adenocarcinoma, where they occur in 1–2% of cases. ROS1 rearrangements are extremely rare in squamous cell lung carcinoma, accounting for less than 0.2% of cases.^[10] The COSMIC database indicated that only 5.33% of squamous cell lung cancer patients have single point mutations in the ROS1 gene (53/995), but no record of squamous cell lung carcinoma patients with tumors harboring ROS1 fusions.^[11]

ROS1-positive adenocarcinoma patients responded better to chemotherapy than NSCLC patients harboring other driver mutations, with an estimated 60% ORR, 89.5% DCR and a 7 month PFS, perhaps due to the sensitivity of ROS1-positive cancers to pemetrexed.^[12-16] This significant pemetrexed susceptibility might arise from the limited number of thymidylate synthetase transcripts in ROS1-positive patients.^[17-20] But then these were adenocarcinoma patients, although Patil T et al^[21] reported a case with significant clinical benefit from pemetrexed-based therapy in ROS1- and ALK-rearranged lung cancer with adeno-squamous histology. Squamous cell lung carcinoma are usually given cytotoxic chemotherapy like paclitaxel, carboplatin, gemcitabine. Receptor tyrosine kinases found in ROS1-positive cancers are druggable targets and TKIs (such as crizotinib) are effective agents for the treatment of these cancers. Yang et al^[22] and Lixia Yu et al^[23] presented a 47 year old and an 84 year old female patient, respectively, with squamous cell lung carcinoma, harboring ROS1 rearrangement, with high sensitivity to crizotinib.

Chromosomal rearrangements of the gene encoding ROS1 proto-oncogene receptor tyrosine kinase define a distinct molecular subgroup of NSCLCs that may be susceptible to therapeutic ROS1 kinase inhibition. ROS1 tyrosine kinase domains present high affinity with the ALK ones, therefore TKIs targeting ALK-rearrangements, crizotinib and lorlatinib, also showed great levels of activity in ROS1 positive patients.^[24,25]

Crizotinib is a small-molecule TKI of anaplastic lymphoma kinase (ALK), ROS1, and another proto- oncogene receptor tyrosine kinase, MET. Crizotinib is a standard treatment for adenocarcinomas with ROS1 rearrangement.^[26] The efficacy and safety of crizotinib in a phase II OxOnc Study in East Asian patients with adenocarcinoma of the lung, showed ORR 71.7%, median PFS of 15.9 months, and median OS of 32.5 months; most TRAEs were grade 1 or 2 in severity.^[27]

TKI resistance remains a major hurdle limiting duration of benefit to these therapies. Lorlatinib is another potent, brain-penetrant, third-generation TKI that targets ALK and ROS1 with preclinical activity against most known resistance mutations in ALK and ROS1. Lorlatinib showed clinical activity in patients with advanced ROS1-positive NSCLC, including those with CNS metastases and those previously treated with crizotinib.^[28] ROS1 mutations (e.g.,G2032R and L2086F) mediate resistance to crizotinib and lorlatinib in over one-third of cases, however.^[29]

From the Foundation Medicine database ROS1 rearranged squamous cell lung cancer patients,^[10] was a non-smoker patient who was treated by durvalumab + tremelimumab immunotherapy under a clinical trial but progressed after 2 cycles. Comprehensive genomic profiling detected a rare oncogenic EZR-ROS1 fusion, and the patient was treated with crizotinib with a significant response within 6

weeks, with complete metabolic response after 42 months therapy.

PD-1/PD-L1 pathway controls the induction and maintenance of immune tolerance within the tumor microenvironment. The activity of PD-1 and its ligands PD-L1 or PD-L2 are responsible for T cell activation, proliferation, and cytotoxic secretion in cancer to degenerating anti-tumor immune responses. The PD-1/PD-L1 axis inhibits T cell activation, proliferation, and survival and cytotoxic secretion within cancer cell. PD-1/PD-L1 axis can be modulated by various signals in cancer cells, which exert a critical role in tumorigenesis. PI3K/AKT pathway, MAPK pathway, JAK/STAT pathway, WNT pathway, NF- κ B pathway and Hedgehog (Hh) pathway promote the expression of PD-1/PD-L1 axis. PD-1/PD-L1-targeted inhibitors have been reported to play a critical role in cancers.^[30]

Among East-Asian patients,^[31] squamous cell lung carcinoma had significantly higher frequency of PD-L1 expression than adenocarcinoma generally (66.9% versus 28.4% of patients with TPS > 1%), while large cell carcinoma had moderate proportion (44.9%) of PD-L1 expression. Overall, PD-L1 exhibited higher expression, as patients developed more advanced TNM stage. High expression of PD-L1 (TPS \geq 50%) occupied 4.9% of stage 0/IA, 17.1% of stage IB, 21.8% for stage II, and 20.0% for stage III/IV.

Pembrolizumab ICI has a role in the first-line treatment of metastatic NSCLC,^[32-34] regardless of histologic subtype or PD-L1 TPS. In patients with PD-L1–negative tumors, pembrolizumab plus chemotherapy has shown a high level of activity as compared with chemotherapy alone. Keynote 401 phase 3 trial^[35] involving patients with untreated metastatic, squamous NSCLC showed that the addition of pembrolizumab to standard chemotherapy with carboplatin and either paclitaxel or nab-paclitaxel, as compared with chemotherapy alone, prolonged median OS by 4.6 months (15.9 months vs. 11.3 months) and median PFS by 1.6 months (6.4 months vs. 4.8 months). The risk of death was 36% lower and the risk of disease progression or death was 44% lower in the pembrolizumab- combination group than in the placebo-combination group. Prolongation of OS of a consistent magnitude was observed across the categories of PD-L1 TPS (<1%, 1 to 49%, and \geq 50%), although the upper limit of the 95% confidence interval for the subgroup with a score of 50% or greater exceeded 1. A higher response rate and longer duration of response were also observed.

The correlation between ROS1 rearrangements and PD-L1 expression or immunotherapy response is the least investigated so far among the druggable translocations in NSCLC. While ROS1 and ALK present high homology in their kinase domains, suggesting a similar effect on PD- L1 expression, there are currently no preclinical data confirming this hypothesis. The effectiveness of immunotherapy in ROS1-positive NSCLC has not yet been fully elucidated. In in vitro experiments, ROS1 was found to regulate the expression of PD-L1 by activating the MEK– ERK and ROS1–SHP2 signaling pathways.^[36]

ROS1 positive tumors were poorly represented even in retrospective case series,^[37-39] preventing any conclusion about PD-L1 expression in this subgroup of patients. Importantly, ROS1 positive NSCLC shares with ALK- and RET- positive counterparts a lower TMB, compared to wild type or EGFR-mutated adenocarcinomas.^[40]

Most ROS1-positive tumors do not express PD-L1 and have a low TMB.^[41] The results of small- sample studies have shown that the ORR of people with ROS1-positive NSCLC receiving mono- immunotherapy was 13%–17%,^[42] and the ORR of immunotherapy combined with chemotherapy was 83%.^[43] Choudhury et al.^[30] found no noticeable differences in the expression levels of PD-L1 between patients who received effective and ineffective immunotherapies. In patients with TKI resistance, combined immunotherapy has a high clinical application value, but potential toxic reactions to sequential immunotherapy with TKIs must be monitored.

High expression of PD-L1 has been reported to be associated with ROS1 rearrangement, but negatively correlated with EGFR mutations.^[44-45] Previous studies have indicated that PD-L1 expression correlates with unfavorable treatment outcomes with EGFR-TKIs.^[46-48] Additionally, several investigations have highlighted that positive PD-L1 expression in ALK- positive NSCLC patients undergoing crizotinib treatment is associated with adverse clinical outcomes.^[49-51] However, the association between PD-L1 expression and crizotinib response in ROS1-positive NSCLC remains ambiguous. Zhang et al^[52] demonstrates a significant association between PD-L1 expression and reduced PFS in patients with advanced NSCLC (only 3.7 % SCC) harboring ROS1 fusions. Conversely, although patients with positive PD-L1 expression exhibited a trend towards decreased OS compared to those with negative PD-L1 expression, this observation did not reach statistical significance. These findings propose that PD-L1 may serve more effectively as a predictive biomarker for crizotinib-induced PFS, rather than as a prognostic biomarker for OS.

Yan H et al^[53] reported a ROS1 positive NSCLC patient, who achieved a continuous PR to immunotherapy plus chemotherapy and a more than 35 months PFS. Nevertheless, another study indicated^[54] that ROS1 fusion NSCLC patients treated with immunotherapy alone displayed an unsatisfactory ORR of 16.7%. In a retrospective Korean study,^[55] 12 ROS1 positive NSCLC patients (among 103, 67% stage IV) received ICIs at some point of their treatment history. ORR was 25% and PFS ranged from 1.1 to 10.7 months.

Chemotherapy combined with immunotherapy with or without bevacizumab may be one of the treatment options for ROS1 positive NSCLC patients after TKI failure.^[56]

Up-regulated PD-L1 expression in NSCLC is correlated with oncogenic RAS signaling, while the tyrosine kinase ROS1 is involved in RAS signaling.^[57, 58] High-level expression of PD-L1 has been associated with ROS1 rearrangement in NSCLC,^[59, 60] which is in line with other studies that PD-L1 expression in NSCLC is driven by aberrant activation of oncogenes (such as EGFR and ALK).^[61-64] Zheng Liu et al^[65] found that PD-L1 expression was up-regulated by ROS1 rearrangement through the MEK-ERK pathway signaling in NSCLC with crizotinib resistance. They suggested that PD-L1/PD-1 blockade as a new strategy for treating crizotinib-resistant NSCLC with ROS1 rearrangement.

PD-L1 upregulation depends on ROS1 fusion more than ROS1-G2032R mutation. ROS1-positive fusion is a key determinant of PD-L1 expression in NSCLCs after crizotinib acquired resistant mutation G2032R. ROS1 modulates PD-L1 expression via common downstream pathways mediated by the ROS1–SHP2 pathway. Oncogenic drivers play a direct role in the induction of PD- L1 expression and thereby contribute to immune escape of NSCLCs. ROS1 fusion NSCLCs show a beneficial ICI therapy response, which lessens in ROS1 G2032R resistance mutation, thus implying that driver genes should be considered when conducting anti-PD-L1/PD-1 ICI therapy to manage lung cancer treatment.^[66]

Responses to single-agent ICI have been reported^[42] in one of seven patients (16.7%) with ROS1 alteration from a retrospective analysis. Interestingly, all the tumors expressed PD-L1, with a strong PD-L1 expression of at least 50% in 60% of the cases.

The efficacy of immunotherapy with or without TKI in PDL-1 overexpressed ROS1 fusion rearranged NSCLC patients remains to be further studied, particularly in squamous cell carcinoma as most literature dwell on adenocarcinoma.

DECLARATION

Ethical Approval and Consent to participate:

A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal. With the patient's consent, ethical approval was given.

Consent for publication:

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images.

Availability of supporting data:

The patient's medical record is available at the hospital for review.

Competing interests:

There is no competing interest on behalf of the authors in reporting this case:

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Authors' contributions:

Prof Ngelangel wrote the case report. Dr Quebec and Dr Timbol assisted Prof Ngelangel in the search and retrieval of medical records and literature relevant to this case. Drs Tan-Reyes, Lapuz, Sy, Tangco, Buensalido and Sandoval-Tan were the multidisciplinary team who took care of the patient, and who reviewed and inputted on the medical case accordingly.

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Prof Corazon A Ngelangel was the medical oncologist of the patient at Asian Cancer Institute- Asian Hospital and Medical Center (ACI-AHMC), and she is Professor at the University of the Philippines-College of Medicine. Dr Mary Kim Quebec was ACI-AHMC Medical Oncology assistant.

Dr. Edith Mari Timbol is medical oncology fellow-in-training at the University of the Philippines- Philippine General Hospital (UPCMPGH), Department of Internal Medicine Division of Medical Oncology. Dr. Jennifer Sandoval-Tan (UPCMPGH) was the medical oncologist of the patient. The patient had the following multidisciplinary team from the AHMC: Dr Michelle Angela Tan-Reyes - pulmonologist, Dr Emelita S Lapuz - cardiologist, Dr. Joseph Adrian L Buensalido - infectious disease (also from UPCMPGH), Dr. John Patrick C See - thoraco-vascular surgeon, Dr. Enrico Tangco - radio-oncologist.

ABBREVIATIONS

NSCLC: Non-small cell lung cancer

SCLC: Small cell lung cancer SCC: Squamous cell carcinoma AC: Adenocarcinoma

LCNEC: Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma ROS1: Reactive oxygen species proto-oncogene 1 EZR-ROS1: Fusion of the Ezrin and ROS1 genes TKI/s: Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitor/s

EGFR: Epithelial growth factor receptor

ALK: Anaplastic lymphoma kinase

BRAF: B-Raf proto-oncogene serine/threonine-protein kinase ERBB2: also known as HER2 or human epidermal growth factor

2 KRAS: Kristen rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog

MS: Microsatellite stability

MET: Mesenchymal epithelial transition

RET: Rearranged-during-transfection translocation

MEK: Mitogen-activated extracellular signal-regulated kinase

ERK: Extracellular signal-regulated kinase

TMB: Tumor Mutational Burden PI3K: Phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase AKT: Protein kinase B

MAPK: Mitogen-activated protein kinase

SHP2: Tyrosine-phosphatase tumor-suppressor

JAK/STAT: Janus kinase/signal transducer and activator of transcription

WNT: Wingless-related integration site

NF- κ B: Nuclear factor kappa B Hh: Hedgehog polypeptide ligand PD-1: Programmed death 1

PDL-1: Programmed death ligand 1 ICI: Immune checkpoint inhibitor TPS: Tumor proportion score

PFS: Progression free survival

OS: Overall survival

ORR: Overall response rate

TRAE: Treatment related adverse effect

EBRT: External beam radiotherapy

CT scan: Computed tomography scan

PET-CT scan: Positron emission tomography CT scan

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